

**MANAGEMENT OF RECURRENT ABORTION BY AYURVEDIC REGIMEN WITH
SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SECONDARY INFERTILITY****Dr. Hemalata Jalgaonkar***

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ABSTRACT

Pregnancy and childbirth are the most important phases of a women's life. It is the start of an incredible journey that leads to great emotional fulfilment to women. Full term births are essential for healthy offspring. To have a successful motherhood continuation of pregnancy is an important as achieving healthy conception. In India, approximately 15% of couples are affected by infertility There are many reasons that prevent a women from being mother and bad obstetric history (BOH) among which TORCH infection (Toxoplasmosis, Rubella, Cytomegalo virus, Heroes simplex) is most common. Recurrent pregnancy loss (RPL) is also known as recurrent miscarriage or habitual abortion. It is defined as two or more consecutive pregnancy losses prior to 20 weeks of pregnancy. The overall TORCH infection rate was 61. 1% while 32% of neonatal mortality was associated with multiple TORCH infections. In *Ayurveda* recurrent pregnancy loss can be correlated with *Garbhasravi Vandhya* mentioned in *Hareetha Samhitha* and *Putraghni yonivyapad* explained in *Brahathrayees* based on clinical features. *Putraghni* is a condition where repeated pregnancy loss occurs because of *artava dosha*, *rakta dosha* and *ati raktasrava*. At the time of the formation of the *Garbha* due to vitiated *shonita*, the product of conception expels repeatedly before attaining viability. It is evident that maternal infection play a vital role in the loss of pregnancy. *Ayurveda* advises to do *Shodhan* therapy ending with *Uttar basti*. In this article, a 26 year old patient with two abortions earlier and a TORCH IgG positive was treated with *shodhan* and *shaman* line of treatment which includes pure herbal medicines for 3 months. The patinet conceived after that and crossed the critical period that is first trimester. During the whole duration of pregnancy *Ayurveda* medications for healthy growth and full term delivery was also continued. thus this article represent *Shodhan* and *shaman* – herbal management in TORCH infection.

KEYWORDS: Vadhyatwa, Garbhasravi Yonivyapad, Infertility, TORCH Infection, Recurrent Abortions.**INTRODUCTION**

Miscarriage is a personal and emotional loss for young couple trying to start a family. It is common problem in childbearing years. According to *Ayurveda* four healthy pillars are require for conception and healthy outcome.^[1] That are *Ritu* (healthy menstrual cycle, fertile period), *Ambu*(proper nutrition) *Kshetra*(healthy endometrium or implantation bed or uterus), *Beeja*(healthy ova or sperm). Deviation from these factors lead to miscarriage and fetal abnormalities lead to infertility. Recurrent pregnancy loss or Habitual abortion can be defined as two or more consecutive miscarriages before 20 weeks gestation.^[2] The common causes responsible for habitual abortion are genetic factors like chromosomal abnormalities, endocrine & metabolic disorders, immunological factors,

lifestyle factor, anatomical abnormalities of reproductive system, environmental toxins, dietary deficiencies & infections^[3], TORCH (Toxoplasmosis, Rubella, Cytomegalovirus, Herpes virus)infection is leading cause of pregnancy loss. *Putraghni* is one of the *yonivyapad* explained in classical texts in which there will be repeated loss of pregnancy.^[4] *Raukshaayad vayu yada garbhum jatam jatam vinashayet*
Dusthta shonitajam naryaha putraghni nama sa mata ^[5]
Acharya charak states that *vayu* gets aggravated due to predominance of *rooksha* properties (*vata kara ahar vihar*) which destroys foetus repeatedly.

Madhur, sheeta, Balya, Jeevaniya, and Rasayan drayas used in such condition.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- 1) To understand the habitual abortion due to TORCH infection W. S. R. to *Putraghni Yoni Vyapad*.
- 2) To access the effect of *ayurvedic* medicines in the management of habitual abortion due to TORCH infection W. S. R to *Putraghni Yoni Vyapad*.

Nidana of Putraghni Yoni Vyapad

Acharya Sushruta says that coitus, travelling in carriage, riding on horse, journey on foot, fear, terror, falling from height, excessive suppression of thirst and hunger, staggering, compression, running, trauma by any weapon, suppression of urge, consumption of excessive dry, hot or pungent diet, grief, diarrhea, excessive use of *kshara*, sitting, standing, sleeping on uneven place or in abnormal posture, emetics, purgatives by all these factors foetus gets detached from uterus just like fruits by its stalk due to trauma this it get aborted.^[6] As fruit falls down untimely due to effect of *krimi* (viral/bacterial infection) *vata* and *abhigata* similarly foetus also gets detached due to influence of all these factors.^[7]

Samprapti

Nidana administration

Vatadi dosh prakopa (vitiation of *Tridoshas*)

Charaka- *Vata* predominance

Sushruta- *Pitta* predominance

Reaches to *Garbhashaya*

Garbh Vinasha (Abortion)

Dosha-*Vata* predominance *Pitta*

Dushya-*Rasa, Rakta, Shukra* (Charak and *Sushruta*)

Roopa-Sthitam Sthitam Hanti Garbham (Repeated destruction of fetus)^[8]

Chikitsa

Garbhasthapaka gana drugs

Madhur, Sheeta, Balya, Jeevaniya and Rasayan dravyas.

Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, immune modulatory drugs are helpful in preventing *Garbhasrava* and maintaining pregnancy.

CASE REPORT

Age-26 yrs female

Occupation – Housewife

Socio-economic status- Middle

Chief complaint – came on 12 th October 2024 with complaint of willing for conception with previous 2 abortions.

Marital status – 3 years ago (NCM)

P/M/H

Menarche-13 years of age

LMP-9/10/2024

4-5 days duration

28-30 days interval

Regular normal flow

Clots and pain absent.

O/H- G2P0L0A2D0

A1- 8 wks missed abortion D and C done in 2023

A2- 7 wks missed abortion D and C done in 2024.

Family History- No similar history of same complaints in family.

No H/O – Medical or Allergic illness.

General Examination

Pulse-60 /min

BP-100/60 mm of hg

Weight-43. 67 kg

Body built-lean

Systemic Examination

RS/CVS- NAD

CNS- Conscious, oriented

P/A -Soft, no organomegaly

Gynaecological examination

Bilateral Breast – Soft, NAD

Inspection of vulva

Pubic hair- Moderate

Redness/ulceration/swelling-Absent

External urethral meatus- Normal

No evidence of pruritus

Per Speculum Examination

Vagina

Redness – Absent

Discharge- Absent

Local lesion- Absent

Cervix-helathy

Erosion- Absent

Per Vaginal Examination

Uterus- anteverted/antiflexed

Normal size

Fornices-free

Tenderness absent

OS- nulliparous

Ashtavidha pareeksha

Nadi-VP

Jihva-saam

Mala-prakrut

Mutra-prakrut

Shabda-prakrut

Drika-prakrut

Aakrti-heen

Sparsh-anushnasheeta

Dasha Vidha Pareeksha

Prakruti-*Vata* *Piitta*

Sara-*Madhyam*

Samhana-*Madhyam*

Pramana-*Dhairgya*-150 cm

Dehabhara-43. 67 kg

Satmya-*Madhyam*

Satva-Madhyam
 Aahara Shakti
 Abhyavarana shakti-Madhyam
 Jarana shakti-Madhyam
 Vyayama shakti-Madhyam
 Vaya-Madhyam
 Vikruti-
 Hetu – katu, amlu, rooksha aahara
 Dosha-Pitta and vata
 Dushya-Rasa, Rakta, Artava
 Desh-sadharan
 Bala-Rogi bala-Madhyam
 Rog Bala-Madhyam

Investigation
 (Done on 18 /10/2024)

Blood group and Rh positive- A positive
 Urine routine and microscopic -NAD
 Hb-11. 2 gm/dl
 WBC-4840/cu. mm
 Pltc-3, 33000/cu. mm
 Sr. tsh-0. 93 uIU/ml
 Serology -Negative
 AMH-7. 55 ng/ml
 FSH-6. 31 mIU/ml
 LH-4. 24 mIU/ml
 PRL-7. 01 ng/ml
 HbA1c-5. 1%
 APLA IgM- Negative
 TORCH-
 Rubella IgG -Positive
 USG(A+P)-Normal

Chikitsa

Date	Complaint	Treatment Given
12/04/2024	Anxious for conception Fear of abortion in next pregnancy. LMP-9/10/2024	TORCH and APLA And other basic investigation.
26/10/2024	LMP-22/11/2024	For 3 Month-(NOV 2024-JAN 2025) Cap. Torchnil 1 BD Tab. KQ 100 1OD Tab. Pushpadhanva 2BD Tab. Leptaden 2 BD Cap. Sujat 1BD Dhanvantar Tail yoni pichu HS Tab. Folvite MB 1OD Shodhan with Yogbasti and Phalghrit Uttarbasti.
23/4/2025	Missed periods in April 2025 Amenorrhea of 6 wks LMP-12/3/2025	UPT- Positive

RESULT

After 3 months of treatment she came with amenorrhea of 6 wks and UPT Positive LMP-12/3/2025. subsequently confirm the pregnancy with USG, as a single intrauterine foetus. EDD-19/12/2025. Patient is coming for regular ANC followup.

USG on 16/5/2025 confirmatory

Reveals a single intrauterine gestation of CGA -9 wks
 FHR-141 bpm. CRL-27 mm EDD-19/12/2025.

USG on 10/06/2025 NT scan

Single intrauterine fetus of gestation 12+4 wks. FHR-148 bpm. Placenta – Anterior. length of cervix-36 mm. Nuchal Translucency- 1. 4 mm
 Nasal Bone -seen and normal
 Double Marker on 11/6/2025- Normal
 USG on 28/7/25 Anomaly scan
 Single live intrauterine fetus. FHR-149 bpm.
 EFW- 290 gms.
 No congenital anomaly noted.

USG on 30 / 09/ 2025 Growth scan

Single live intrauterine fetus
 FHR-140 bpm
 EFW- 1120 gm

AFI-14

Placenta-Anterior
 Doppler-Normal
 GTT-Normal

DISCUSSION

Becoming mother is the most cherish dream of all women. *Ritu, Ambu, Kshetra, Beeja* are the 4 essential factors for the fertility. defect in any one of them will cause infertility. *Vata* is the prime cause of any abortion. In *putraghni yonivyapad Beeja* and *Kshetra* plays major role. Habitual abortion takes place due to *Ruksha Ahar* and *Vihar* this leads to *vata prakopa* which inturn causes *shonita* and *Artav Dushti* results in *Garbha vinash*. This medicines used in this study have *Garbhasthapaka gana* and *Madhur, sheeta, balya, Jeevaniya, and Rasayan* this help preventing *garbhasrava* and maintaing pregnancy.

Here in this case,

Shaman chikitsa

Cap. Torchnil

Content-*Yashtimadhu, Guduchi, Laghu Kantakari, Brihat Kantakari, Pippali, Gokshuru, Bharang Mool, Dadim Patra, Usheer, Rasna, Manjishtha*

Cap Torchoil is having antioxidant action by which it corrects the oxidative damage at placental level & thus

prevents abortion. The contents of Torchnil cap have antiviral & antimicrobial action & acts as a immunomodulator.

Tab. KQ 100

Content-Co-enzyme Q-10, MUFA, PUFA, L-arginine, Omega 3 Fatty Acids, EPA, DHA, Ubidecarenone, Natural Mixed carotenoids, Zinc Sulphate, Piperine, Lycopene, Vitamin B12, Selenium
These are essential for the immune system's proper functioning and is vital in building and repairing tissue. enhances the chances of fertility.

Pushpadhanwa Ras

Content -*Mulethi, Vangabhasma, Abhrakbhasma, Ras Sindoor, Nagbhasma*. Helps to regulate the ovarian function, follicular maturation acts as rejuvenator, Balances the harmones in the body.

Tab. Leptaden

Content-*Jeevanti, Kambhoj*

Preventing abortion by inhibiting biosynthesis of PGF2a from uterine musculature. It helps in implantation of fertilized ovum and improve the environmental factor for nidation thus helping in sustenance of pregnancy.

Tab. sujat

Content-*Amla, Ashwagandha, Gokhru*

Sujat capsules aim to improve the placental function by managing oxidative damage. As an effective anti-oxidant, it manages oxidative stress during pregnancy.

Shodhan chikitsa

Snehan Swedan- Abhyang followed by *Ushna Jal Snaan*.

Yogbasti was given for 8 days for 3 consecutive cycle.

Anuvasan Basti was given with *Sahachar Tail* 80 ml for 5 days.

Niruh Basti was given with *Dashmuladi Kwath* 960 ml for 3 days.

Dashmuladi kwath(*Dashmul, Erundmul, Triphala*)
Shatpushpa kalk, Sahachar Tail, Madh, Saindhav)

Uttarbasti was administered after cessation of menstruation i. e. on 5th 7th and 9th menstrual cycle with *Phalaghrut* 5 ml for 3 days of 3 consecutive months.

Mode of action of *Yogbasti*

Basti is the best *Panchakarma* procedure for *vatarog* as per *Ayurvedic* classic. *Yogbasti* with *Dashmul kwath* was used as *Niruh basti* because *Dashmul* has been proved *uttam Vataghana* and *Shahchar tail* is also best drug *dravya* for *Vandhyatwa*. Probably these all clear the pathogenesis of anovulation.

Sneha Basti given through *Guda* (rectal route) normalizes *Apana Vayu* leading to *Vatanulornak* and physiological functioning of *Vata*. Which may help in turn for the extrusion of ovum from the follicle and ovulation. *Basti Dravya* spreads all over the body,

pacifies the aggravated *Dosha* along with *Vyan Vayu* (one of the five subtypes of *Vata* which distributed blood and nutrients to different parts of the body through blood circulation) leads to *Samyak Rasa Raktadi Dhatu Nirmana* (proper formation of body tissues). *Sukshma bhaga* (fine part) of *Rasa* reaches the *Bijagranthi* (ovary), which regularizes the *Beejotsarga* (ovulation) with the help of normal *Apana Vayu*.^[9] The women having amenorrhea, scanty menstruation, non ovulation or useless ovulation (Ovum with minimal or absence of capacity of fertilization) etc. causes of infertility should prescribed *Anuvasan*. By use of *basti* the *yoni* becomes healthy, even sterile women conceive. The *basti* is beneficial to the women having repeated abortions, short lived and weak children.

Mode of action of *Uttarbasti*

According to *Acharyas*. *Uttarbasti* should be given after cleaning her body by use of 2-3 *shodhan basti* so in three consecutive cycle after three *Yogbasti, Uttarbasti* were given.

Due to normalization of *Vata* by the use of *Uttarbasti* the *yoni* retains the *Garbha* quickly for the woman conceive immediately, so it means *Uttarbasti* prepare the *Kshetra* for *Garbha dharan*.

Uttarbasti given in intrauterine route activates the normal function of *Vata* and stimulates the ovarian hormone ultimately achieving ovulation. Also it nourishes the Endometrium which helps in implantation. Probably *Uttarbasti* stimulates these receptors so that proper maturation of follicle and ovulation occur in each cycle. *Uttarbasti* acting directly on the *shtana* of the pathogenesis of this disease ie. *Yoni*. *Uttarbasti* is indicated in *Yonivyapad, Garbhashaya vikar*.

Basti normalize the function of *Apan Vayu* leading to normal *Raja* and normal *Beeja nirmana*. *Triphala* had property of *Balya*. *Deepan. Pachana, Yonivishodhan Artavajanara* and *Beejotsarga*.

Properties of *Phalaghrut*

Sharangdhar, Vagabhatta, Yogratnakar and *Bhavprakash* mentioned in the treatment of *vyandhyatwa*. *Vandhyatwa* is *vata* dominated *sannipataj* vyadhi. *Ghruta* is *Tridoshaghna* due to its properties and milk is also *Vata-Pitta shamak, Jivaniya* and *Rasayana*, So *Phalaghrut* has properties of *Ghruta*, milk other ingredients. *Phalaghruta* contains mainly *Tikta, Madhura* and *Katu rasa, Laghu, Snighdha* both *Katu* and *Madhur vipak* and also *Ushna* and *Sheet virya*. It also has *Deepan, Pachana, Lekhana, Anulomana, Shothhar, Krimighna, Balya, Prajashtapan* action and *yoni pradoshanashak* properties which works mainly on female reproductive system. Due to *Balya, Vrishya* and *Rasayana* properties of *Phalaghrut* it regulates the function of HPO axis.

This *Phalaghrut* is *Pruthvi Mahabhut* predominance which increases the *dharan* capacity of *Garbhashay* and

nourishes the *Garbhashay* for conception and decreases the chances of miscarriage, still birth and preterm baby.^[10] Hence *Phalaghrut* was used for *Uttarbasti*.

Yoni pichu^[11]

Vaginal drug delivery possesses systemic as well as local action. The blood cells are abundant in vaginal wall. This vascularity of vaginal tissue is responsible for first uterine pass effect, or direct preferential vaginal to uterine transport. When drugs are absorbed in vagina, it passes to uterus by osmolarity of *Sneha*. The *Sneha* which remains in inner portion of vagina may show systemic effect by being absorbed and transported into inferior vena cava by vaginal, retro sigmoidal, vesical and uterine veins. *Yoni Pichu Kriya* is indicated in *Vataja* and *Pittaja Yonivyapada Chikitsa*. *Vandhyatva* due to Endometrial factor is *Tridoshaja* condition that's why *Yoni Pichu*.

In *Ayurvedic* classics like *vaidya yoga ratnavali*, *sarvaroga chikitsa ratnam* and in *sahasrayogam Dhanvantari taila* is indicated for all *yonivyapats* and *prajastapana*. The main ingredient *Bala moola*(*Sida acuta*)” is *pittavata hara*, *balya*, *grahi* and has *prajastapana* properties. *Dasamoolas* are *vata slesma hara*, *agnimantha*, *syonaka*, *gambhari*, *gokshuru*, *kantakari*, *sariva*, *mashaparni*, *saindava lavana*, *manjista*, *kusta*, *satapuspa*, *tagara* all these have *deepana*, *pachana* and has *tikta*, *kashaya rasas*. *Tikta ras* is best in *amapachana* and *kashaya rasa* is *pakva pitta soshanam*, so It acts as best *pittahara oushadam*. Given dosage form is a *taila* preparation, *taila* used is *tila taila* which is *tridosha hara* and is *grahi* and *balya*. *Taila* with its *sneha* and *sukshma gunas* is easily absorbable through the mucus membrane, glands and vessels. By its steroidal action of drugs in the *danwantari taila* it gives nutrition and may potentiate the endometrial receptors. It is more effective and easily absorbable hence it is effective in all major causes of infertility of different dosha vitiation.^[12,13]

This, the treatment given to the patient was on the basis of *ayurvedic* principles and the outcome of the treatment was very good.

CONCLUSION

Habitual abortion is a common complication of pregnancy contributing significantly to maternal morbidity. A miscarriage causes a great emotional setback to a couple. The incidence of pregnancy loss is increased after each miscarriage.

TORCH infections are the one among the major cause for early pregnancy loss & congenital birth defects. As compared to before, the incidence of habitual abortions & TORCH infection are increased due to modern stressful lifestyle & food habits. Here in present case study, a positive case of TORCH infection is treated by *ayurvedic* treatment only. Pregnancy is successfully carried as it crossed that critical period of first trimester.

The medicines used here alleviates *tridoshas* specially *pitta* & *vata* & having *garbhashapaka*, *rasayana* & *balya* properties. Thus, helps to maintain pregnancy & promotes the growth of fetus.

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